

An Emerging Tech Innovation in Indian Banking with Artificial Intelligence Application: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

Demis Hassabis CEO of google DeepMind calls AI as 'the science of making machines smart'.

Artificial Intelligence in banking and other financial sectors is showing signs of interest and adoption. AI will enable financial services companies to completely redefine how they work, create innovative products and services and transform customer experiences.

AI is set to have a truly positive impact on people by removing monotonous repetitive task from day to day work. A bank can expect potential savings of between 20 to 25 percent across IT operations including infrastructure, maintenance and development cost.

A digital boom is certainly taking place across all segments of banking thus making the operations more hassle free and impactful, creating a leaner system to work on but certainly with challenges.

These are some of the areas of AI applications in banking sector:

Block chain, digital payments, IOT, AI, Machine learning, BOTs, robotic process automation, smart wallets, underwriting

This paper highlights the importance of technology, challenges, opportunities and new innovations in Indian banking sector with the use artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Innovation, AI application, future of AI in Indian banking, banking sector, digitalization, technology, challenges.

Machine Learning has just turned into another innovation. It has become a part of our day to day lines. Banking sector has long approached fresh information and data utilizing that information to accomplish productivity and provide better administration.

Change does not damage people it pushes people to improve and settle for choices that are brilliant. Technology continues to drive the organizational change agenda, but now its making operations smarter and autonomous. There is a primarily shift from humans consuming data to machines consuming data.

Banking Sector is becoming one of the first adopter of AI, banks are exploring and implementing the technology in various way that’s why.

Artificial Intelligence in banking especially in India should consider technology.

According to the recent report of 2018 is 83% of Indian Banking Bankers believe that AI will work along with the humans in the next two years with a higher than global average of 79%.

93% of Indian banks said they are using data to drive critical and automated decision making. Indian Banks including SBI have started deploying AI in a big way to improve efficiency, detect human behavior and reduce operational cost.

SBI the India’s Largest lender has SBI intelligent assistant (SIA). A smart chat assistant evolved from the cutting edge technology of AI that resolves queries of NRI customers similarly to the GA bank representative. The Indian banking sector is on a rapid digital journey.

AI Application in Indian Banking Sector

1) SBI Code for bank

A national hackathon for developers, start ups and students to come up with innovative ideas and solution for the banking sector, focusing on technologies such as predictive analytics, fintech/ blockchair, digital payments, IOT, AI, Machine learning, BOTS, Robotics process automation.

2) Axis bank: Innovation lab “Thought factory” and AI & NLP (Natural language processing). Thought Factory - In house innovation team and accelerator program through which the bank engages with start ups in 3 month programs. For fine tuning, validation and scattng their business.

AI & NLP – an app to help customers with financial and non financial transactions.

3) HDFC bank - Eva [AI BASED CHAT BOT]

Eva can assimilate knowledge from thousands of sources and provide simple answers in less than 0.4 seconds. Within the first few days of its launch, Eva has answered more than 1,00,000 queries from thousands of customers from IT countries across the globe.

ICICI Bank - Robotic Software

A Kind of software generally focused on automating office work. Software robots which emulate human actions to automate and perform repetitive high-volume and time-consuming business task.

Through machine learning AI can effortlessly consume and process large amounts of data at an expedited level.

Its immense speed brings efficiency to financial services and as it continues to learn and become even more efficient it can identify more patterns than before, providing scope for customized offerings to customers .

Banks assist customers to hedge their risks and furnish them with financial advice .Banks also process millions of cashless payments everyday –error-free and very inexpensively. A modern economy cannot survive without an efficient and safe circulation of money.

Opportunities

AI applications is banking to look out for in next 5 years

1. AML Pattern detection
Anti Money Laundering refers to set of procedures, laws or regulations designed to stop the practice of generating income through illegal actions.
2. Chat bots
Chat bots are artificial intelligence based automated chat system, which stimulate human chats without any human interventions
They work by identifying the context and emotions in text chat by the human end user and respond to them with most appropriate reply.
3. Algorithmic trading
Plenty of hedge funds across the globe are using high end systems to deploy AI models which learn by taking input from several sources of variation in financial markets to make investment decision.
4. Fraud detection
It is one of the key areas in banking sector where AI systems excelled the most.
An early example of successful implementation of data analysis techniques in the banking industry is the FICO Falcon fraud assessment system.
5. Customer Recommendations
Recommendations engines are a key contribution of AI in banking sectors. It is based on using the data from past about users and various offerings from bank like credit card plans, investment strategies, funds etc.,

Challenges

AI has helped to push the envelope in terms of technological advancements in the financial industry. For example, consumers can use financial recognition to login to financial apps and use voice commands to check their balances. AI is said to disrupt the industry even further. Financial institutions must repeatedly test AI platforms rather than merely looking at slides or sales pictures.

- Availability of right data
Data is the lifeblood of AI and any vulnerability arising from unverified information is a serious concern for business
- Different languages in India
Applications which use speech to text or text to speech rely on natural language processing libraries and techniques but in order to effectively reach out to wider population in India much more progress is required on NLP front.
- Data Privacy
Data access data privacy is a central aspect of any AI works bank do. India has their own data regulations. Banks in India will have to build AI systems with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulations) and simulate regulations in mind.
- Scarcity of trained Human Resources
The existing workforce is not familiar with latest tools and applications. It is one of the important challenges that is faced by industry and not just banks in India

Conclusion

The union finance minister in his budget speech for FY 2016-2017, announced several measures to support consolidation of public sector banks. An allocation of Rs 25,000 Crore was made for FY 2016-2017 towards recapitalization of public sector banks, which could be increased if required.

Leading upto 2020, radically transformed Banks models will emerge. A glimpse ahead shows an emphasis on innovative technologies to vastly facilitate banking – inclusive banking through new types of bank models, non – traditional alliances to make banking affordable, Fintech capabilities to make banking customer centric. Banking in the future will be collaborative, exciting and will raise the bar in setting new standards.

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